

FREEDAM connections: advanced finite element modelling

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SUMMARY: *FREEDAM connections consist of a symmetric friction device connecting the lower flange of the beam to the column by means of L-Stub. This assembly prevents the damage of the connected members and dissipates energy by means of the slippage between the clamped steel elements and the friction pads of the device. In order to characterize the monotonic and cyclic performance of the joints equipped with friction dampers a comprehensive and extensive parametric finite element (FE) simulations have been carried. The FE models have been validated against the experimental results of the tests carried out within the FREEDAM project. The performed FE analyses allowed evaluating the response of both external and internal joints with the FREEDAM devices. In addition, different geometries of the friction dampers and the relevant beam-column assemblies have been investigated. The FE analyses confirmed the effectiveness of the design assumptions and the satisfactory performance of the investigated joints.*

KEYWORDS: *steel joints, beam-to-column connections, seismic response, friction damper, finite element analyses.*

1 Introduction

Steel Moment Resisting Frames (MRFs) are ductile and dissipative structural systems that can guarantee excellent seismic performance if properly designed and the joints are properly detailed [Latour and Rizzano, 2013, Giordano *et al.*, 2017, Piluso *et al.*, 2019, Di Benedetto *et al.*, 2020, Elettore *et al.*, 2021, Lemons *et al.*, 2018, Manganiello *et al.*, 2021, Montuori *et al.*, 2020 and 2021, Tartaglia *et al.*, 2020a and 2022a]. However, exploiting their large source of ductility implies accepting severe damage into main members to which large residual drifts are unavoidably associated. As a direct result, structures exhibiting an excellent seismic performance may require expensive refurbishment and repairing costs that might be impractical and unsustainable, thus leading to a more favorable demolition after severe earthquake.

The recent earthquakes occurred in New Zealand (e.g., Christchurch 2010) clearly highlighted this issue. Therefore, research into new techniques to prevent or limit structural damage to buildings has gained relevance. The global tendency has been a shift towards the development and implementation of low damage seismic resisting systems [Di Lauro *et al.*, 2019, Santos *et al.*, 2019 and 2020] in order to reduce the economic effects of earthquakes so that, any minor damage may be easily and cheaply repaired thus preventing the collapse of the building and guaranteeing that it quickly becomes operational.

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The main goal of FREEDAM project was to develop and validate novel bare steel connections equipped with friction dampers that prevent damage to the connected members and dissipate energy by means of the slippage into clamped steel elements and friction pads. A wide range of tests and analytical studies were carried out within the FREEDAM project to assess the dampers performance under static and dynamic action; moreover, the behaviour of the FREEDAM joints was also tested when subjected to impact loading [D'Antimo M. *et al.*, 2019, D'Antimo M. *et al.*, 2020].

In order to characterize the mechanical response of the FREEDAM joints refined and advanced finite element (FE) simulations have been carried. Indeed, a wide range of studies demonstrated that finite element analyses can be effectively used to predict the nonlinear behavior of bolted joints giving an accurate description of the loading paths in the joint components [Landolfo, 2022]. In addition, parametric analyses have been carried out to widen the results of the experimental campaign investigating the (i) type of friction damper (i.e., horizontal and vertical friction damper), (ii) the beam-column assemblies and (iii) the joint configuration (i.e., internal and external).

Therefore, an extensive parametric numerical study was carried out on the basis of finite element simulations properly calibrated on the experimental results.

The paper is organized in three main parts, as follows: (i) the first part summarizes the design procedure of the FREEDAM joints; (ii) the second part reports is mainly concentrated on the numerical modelling assumptions; thus, all the FE modelling assumptions and their validation; (iii) the third part describes the results of the parametric FE analyses.

2 Conception and design criteria of FREEDAM joints

The bending resistance of friction connection (FC) is mainly governed by the friction coefficient of the pads and the clamping force applied to the pre-loaded bolts. Therefore, the resistance of FC could theoretically vary with the required capacity of all beam-to-column assemblies keeping the same friction pad (i.e. considering the same values of the friction coefficient) but changing the clamping force in the bolts. However, this simplistic criterion cannot be adopted because the clamping bolts of the device have an optimal range of preload to guarantee the effectiveness of the friction mechanism and stability of hysteretic response. Therefore, the number and the diameter of the bolts of the friction dampers depend on the required moment resistance of the joint and the dimensions of the connected members. Figure 1 shows the two types of friction joints seismically pre-qualified within the FREEDAM research project, namely with horizontal (Fig. 1a) and vertical (Fig. 1b) damper.

To simplify the design and the use of FREEDAM joints, a set of five friction dampers with vertical friction surface was conceived to cover a wide range of applications for Eurocode-compliant steel multistorey MRFs. These dampers have been designed to provide different flexural resistances through the moment utilization factors “ m ” (i.e. the ratio between the design moment of the FC over the plastic moment of the connected beam) and the beam section (which comprises European IPE profiles, but it can be extended to different shapes with similar plastic modulus and depth). The ranges of “ m ” and beam profiles were derived from the results of a previous numerical study [Nastri *et al.*, 2019].

The five different dampers are referred hereinafter as D1-to-D5 and their geometrical features are shown in Figure 2. These systems were designed accounting for the following assumptions:

- S355 steel grade for plates and angles;
- High-strength preloaded bolts grade 10.9;
- Characteristic dynamic friction coefficient “ $\mu_{d,k}$ ” equal to 0.53 as given in [Ferrante *et al.*, 2018a, and Francavilla *et al.*, 2020];
- Upper bound dynamic friction coefficient “ $\mu_{d,ub}$ ” equal to 0.84 as given in [Ferrante *et al.*, 2018a, and Francavilla *et al.*, 2020];
- The safety factor accounting for the loss of initial preload due to short-term and long-term relaxation phenomena γ_{creep} is assumed equal to 1.15 in accordance with [Ferrante *et al.* 2018b];
- The optimal range of bolt clamping force set equal to 0.4-0.6 $F_{p,C}$ as observed by [Ferrante *et al.*, 2018a, and Francavilla *et al.*, 2020], being $F_{p,C}$ the design preload in accordance with EN1993-1-8;
- The range of utilization factor m for the joint set equal to 0.3-0.6 of the plastic bending capacity of the connected beam ($M_{pl,beam}$).

The design force of the friction damper is obtained as the ratio between the design bending moment and the lever arm of the FC, namely as given by Eq.(1):

$$F_{D,Ed} = \frac{M}{z} = \frac{m \cdot M_{pl,beam}}{z} \quad (1)$$

More details on the design procedure of friction damper, including also the requirements for serviceability conditions, can be found in [Piluso *et al.*, 2020], while all geometrical features of the proposed dampers are given in Table 1 and in Figure 2.

$$F_{D,Rd} \geq F_{D,Ed} \rightarrow \frac{\mu_{d,k} \cdot n_s \cdot n_b \cdot F_p}{\gamma_{creep}} \geq \frac{m \cdot M_{pl,beam}}{z} \quad (2)$$

where F_p is the design bolt preload, n_b is the number of bolts specific for each damper, n_s is the number of friction surfaces. Manipulating Eq. (2), once selected the optimal range of bolt preload it can be easily obtained the minimum number of bolts that should be properly rounded up in pairs to make technologically feasible the damper.

Once the geometry of the dampers (in terms of bolt properties and lever arm) is selected, the non-dissipative components of the joints (i.e. T- and L-Stub connections) should be designed to resist the forces associated to the following friction force:

$$F_{D,ub,d} = \mu_{st,ub} \cdot n_s \cdot n_b \cdot F_{p,ub} \quad (2)$$

where the upper bound bolt preload was set equal to 1.2.

The resistance of T- and L-Stub connections is evaluated in accordance with EN 1993-1-8, but their relevant design forces (i.e. tension and shear forces) are evaluated.

In order to make ease of selection of the most appropriate damper, Table 1 reports the range of application of each type of damper on the basis of the beam section and the moment utilization factors m .

Figure 1 - Freedom Joints with horizontal and vertical friction dampers

Figure 2 - The geometrical features of the investigated damper

Table 1 - Design range of the considered dampers

Beam Size	Bending utilization factor (m)			
	≤ 0.3	$0.3 < (m) \leq 0.4$	$0.4 < (m) \leq 0.5$	$0.5 < (m) \leq 0.6$
IPE 270	-	-	D1	D1
IPE 300	-	D1	D1	D1
IPE 360	D1	D1	D2	D2
IPE 400	D1	D2	D2	D2
IPE450	D1	D2	D2	D3
IPE 500	D2	D2	D3	D3
IPE 550	D2	D3	D3	D4
IPE 600	D2	D3	D4	D4
IPE 750 × 147	D3	D4	D5	D5
IPE 750 × 161	D3	D4	D5	D5
IPE 750 × 173	D3	D4	D5	D5
IPE750×196+	D4	D5	D5	D5

3 Modelling assumptions

The finite element models (FEMs) were developed by means of Abaqus 6.14 [Simulia, 2015] and the main modelling hypothesis are in line with those formerly described by the Authors in their previous studies [Tartaglia *et al.*, 2021a, 2021b].

The effectiveness of the modelling assumptions was also verified by comparing the performed simulations to the experimental results conducted within the FREEDAM research project.

3.1 Modelling assumptions

The beam-to-column joints geometry was set considering the sub-assembly shown in Fig. 3a. All elements were modelled as solid parts and meshed using the C3D8R finite element (an 8-node linear brick with reduced integration). The mesh density was set on the basis of sensitivity analyses conducted by [Tartaglia *et al.*, 2018]. In particular, for bolts, plates and steel profiles, the maximum element dimension was respectively assumed equal to 5 mm, 10 mm and 20 mm (see Figure 3b). Both geometrical and mechanical nonlinearities were accounted for as shown in [Tartaglia *et al.*, 2020, 2022b].

Figure 3: Features of FE model

The steel material properties were modelled based on the coupon tests performed in the laboratory as part of the experimental campaign of FREEDAM project. The yield stress was set equal to 380 MPa for beams, 427 MPa for columns and 443MPa for both L-stub and T-stubs. The elastic modulus was assumed equal to 210000MPa and Poisson's coefficient equal to 0.3.

Both nonlinear kinematic and isotropic plastic hardening was modelled as described in [Cassiano *et al.*, 2017 and 2018].

The bolts were modelled as shown by [D'Aniello *et al.*, 2016 and 2017], and the amount of the preload force was set equal to the experimentally measured value.

The contacts between all parts were modelled with Normal Behaviour to avoid overclosure (by means of the "Hard Contact" option) and Tangential behaviour to define the relative sliding (by means of the Coulomb friction law). Moreover, to simulate the partial loss of the friction coefficient due to the smoothing of the superficial roughness of the friction pad, the temperature-dependent friction laws were used, thus friction coefficient decreases with the increase of temperature because of continuous sliding of plates. The reference friction properties were assumed equal to 0.59 [Zimbru *et al.*, 2018]. Tie constraints have been used

to mimic in a simplified manner the full penetration welds. This simplified hypothesis is acceptable since no plastic deformations occur in the welds.

Quasi-static analyses were carried out by using the Dynamic Implicit solver. The analyses were performed considering two loading steps: (i) bolt loading and (ii) displacement history.

3.2 Validation

The effectiveness of the numerical assumptions was verified by comparing both the deformed shapes and the cyclic moment rotation curves obtained from the FE analyses with the experimental results [Latour *et al.*, 2018]. The main geometrical features of the tested joints are summarized in Table 2, where the joints are identified using the following codes FD-1-1, FD-1-2, FD-2-1 and FD-2-2.

Table 2 - Tested beam-to-column assemblies

Joint ID	Connection type	Column	Beam	Internal level arm mm
FD-1-1	Type 1	HE 220M	IPE 270	478
FD-1-2	Type 1	HE 500M	IPE 450	710
FD-2-1	Type 2	HE 220M	IPE 270	458
FD-2-2	Type 2	HE 500M	IPE 450	710

Figure 4 - Comparison between the experimental and numerical results in terms of moment rotation curves

The boundary conditions of the joints, as well as the beams and the columns lengths, have been accurately defined in order to replicate the experimental setup. Moreover, the beam was laterally restrained with out-of-plane restraints located in the same sections of the experimental setup.

The AISC 341-16 loading protocol up to 6% interstorey drift ratio was applied at the beam end consistently with the test procedure.

As it can be observed (see Fig. 4) for the FE models accurately predict the response of all examined joints in terms of elastic stiffness, resistance and shapes of hysteretic loops. Moreover, as it can be observed in Figure 5 coherently with [Tartaglia *et al.*, 2021b], the joints behave almost in the elastic range with some minor plastic deformations concentrated in the upper T-Stubs of the joint and in in the two lower L-Stubs.

Figure 5 - Von Mises stress (S) and equivalent plastic deformation ($PEEQ$) distribution on the F1-1 and F2-1 beam-to-column joints

4. Parametric FE simulations

To investigate the effectiveness of FREEDAM joints for different beam-to-column assemblies and geometry of the friction dampers a wide range of parametric FE simulations have been carried out. In particular, three sets of beam-to-column assemblies were selected varying the depth of the members to cover the cases of shallow, intermediate and deep profiles.

The lengths of columns and beams are reported in Table 3 and were assumed to be representative of the MRFs analysed by [Nastri *et al.*, 2019, Maglio *et al.*, 2021].

To identify the investigated joints, the adopted nomenclature was in function of the dimension of the investigated damper (D1, D2, D3 D4 and D5), the dimensions of the beam-column assembly (A, B or C) and the location of the joint in the frame (i.e., internal “X” or external “T”). For the sake of example, the X-D2-B acronym corresponds to an internal joint equipped with a D2 damper and intermediated beam (i.e., IPE450).

Table 3 summarizes all examined cases. It can be observed that the only difference between the T and X-joint is the size of the column.

Table 3 - Investigated beam-to-column joints assemblies

ID	Beam	Column	ID	Beam	Column	$L_{beam} / 2$ [mm]	L_{column} [mm]
T-D1-A	IPE270	HE 240 B	X-D1-A	IPE270	HE 280 B	3000	3500
T-D1-B	IPE360	HE 360 B	X-D1-B	IPE360	HE 400 B	3000	3500
T-D1-C	IPE450	HE 240 B	X-D1-C	IPE450	HE 500 B	3000	3500
T-D2-A	IPE360	HE 360 B	X-D2-A	IPE360	HE 400 B	3000	3500
T-D2-B	IPE450	HE 360 B	X-D2-B	IPE450	HE 500 B	3000	3500
T-D2-C	IPE600	HE 320 M	X-D2-C	IPE600	HE 600 M	3000	3500
T-D3-A	IPE400	HE 300 B	X-D3-A	IPE400	HE 450 B	3000	3500
T-D3-B	IPE550	HE 500 M	X-D3-B	IPE550	HE 550 M	3000	3500
T-D3-C	IPE750X147	HE 500 M	X-D3-C	IPE750X147	HD_400x592	3000	3500
T-D4-A	IPE500	HE 280 M	X-D4-A	IPE500	HE 450 M	4000	4000
T-D4-B	IPE550	HE 500 M	X-D4-B	IPE550	HE 600 M	4000	4000
T-D4-C	IPE750X196+	HE 650 M	X-D4-C	IPE750X196+	HD_400x818	4000	4000
T-D5-A	IPE600	HE 320 M	X-D5-A	IPE600	HE 600 M	4000	4000
T-D5-B	IPE750X147	HD 400x634	X-D5-B	IPE750X147	HD_400x634	4000	4000
T-D5-C	IPE750X196+	HE 650 M	X-D5-C	IPE750X196+	HD_400x818	4000	4000

The numerical results of all investigated joints were discussed in terms of moment-rotation curves, Von Misses stress distribution and equivalent plastic deformation (PEEQ).

4.1 Results for external joints

Figure 6 depicts the results of the external joints under hogging and sagging moments up to a rotation of 5%, where the beam plastic moment ($M_{pl,beam}$) and the moment utilisation factors (m) were also reported.

It can be observed that the joint bending capacity is always consistent with the relevant design bending moment. However, a slight asymmetric behaviour can be noted due an increase of resistance under hogging moments. This different response is mainly due to the higher deformability of the L-stubs. In fact, when the joint is under hogging moment, the deformations of the L-stub lead to an increase of contact forces between the clamped parts of the dampers and a consequent increase of friction resistance.

Figure 6 - Moment-rotation curves of the T-Joints under hogging and sagging moments

Figure 7 -Von Misses stress and equivalent plastic deformation distribution at hogging and sagging rotation equal to 5%

Figure 7 depicts the distribution of both Von Mises stress and PEEQ distribution at a rotation of 5%. Coherently with the design hypotheses, the column and the beams behave elastically but minor plastic deformations occur into the upper part of the beam web as well as on the T-Stub (where the theoretical centre of rotation is located). In all investigated cases the magnitude of plastic deformations in the connection is rather small and very close to the yield strain.

All bolts connecting the beam and the column to the stiffeners and to the T-Stub behave in elastic range with the only exception of the bolts belonging to the dampers; indeed, in this case, small plastic deformations can be observed in the mid-length of the shank, for large value of rotation (0.04 rad and 0.05 rad). However the bolts close to the column face do not exhibit plastic deformation since the plates of the L-stub connection are not fully rigid and the demand on the bolts is not uniform; and because their relatively smaller friction resistance that allows them sliding for smaller forces than the other bolts.

4.2 Results for internal joints

Internal joints exhibit almost the same behaviour of the external ones, since the column web panel remains in the elastic range and the non-linear mechanism develops only into the FREEDAM dampers. Therefore, for the sake of brevity, it is solely shown the comparison between the response of T and X joints alternatively equipped with haunched (i.e., horizontal friction mechanism) and vertical rib (i.e., vertical friction mechanism) damper.

Figure 8 - Moment rotation curves (a and c) and Von Mises stress (S) distribution (b and d), of internal X-joints

Figures 8a and c show the moment-rotation response curves of the joints with haunched and vertical rib damper respectively. The differences are negligible and are mainly due to the different overall rigidity of the column, which is stiffer in the case of internal joints. Thus, at the same imposed chord rotation the rotational contribution of the column is lower, and the slip of the damper is slightly greater as well as its corresponding reaction.

The deformed shape and the stress distributions are almost the same for both T and X joints as it can be observed comparing the distribution of Von Mises stress in Figure 8b and d (configurations with haunched and vertical rib damper, respectively), and in Figure 7.

Conclusions

Parametric finite element simulations of steel beam-to-column joints with FREEDAM devices were carried out varying: (i) the connection typologies (with horizontal and vertical friction damper), (ii) the beam-column assembly, (iii) the dampers dimension and (iv) the joint configuration (internal and external).

Based on the obtained results, the following consideration can be summarized:

- The numerical models are able to predict accurately the elastic stiffness, resistance and cyclic behaviour of FREEDAM joints with horizontal and vertical friction damper.
- The moment rotation curves are almost symmetric under both hogging and sagging moments. However, under hogging moment, and for large value of rotation (about 0.04 rad) an increase of 25% of the joint resistance was observed in all investigated cases. This asymmetric behaviour is mainly due to the deformability of the L-stubs clamped to the friction pad of the device.
- The steel parts of the joints behave almost in the elastic range. Indeed, no plastic deformations were observed in both beams and columns, while minor plastic strains can occur in the T-Stub and L-Stubs.
- The effectiveness of the investigated friction dampers is replicable for all beam-to-column assemblies within the range of investigated parameters.
- All considerations made for the external joints can be extended to the internal joints. However, it should be observed a small increase of elastic stiffness and resistance due to a larger column as respect to the corresponding internal joints.

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Conessioni FREEDAM: modelli avanzati agli elementi finiti

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SUMMARY: *Le connessioni FREEDAM sono costituite da un dispositivo ad attrito simmetrico che collega la flangia inferiore della trave alla colonna per mezzo di angolari ad L opportunamente bullonati. Questo assieme evita il danneggiamento degli elementi collegati e dissipa l'energia per mezzo dello scorrimento tra gli elementi in acciaio serrati dai bulloni e le superfici di attrito del dispositivo. Al fine di caratterizzare la risposta monotona e ciclica dei nodi dotati di dissipatori ad attrito è stato condotto un esteso studio parametrico basato su analisi ad elementi finiti. I modelli sono stati validati rispetto ai risultati sperimentali dei test effettuati nell'ambito del progetto FREEDAM. Le analisi ad elementi finiti hanno consentito di valutare la risposta dei nodi con i dispositivi FREEDAM sia esterni che interni. Inoltre, sono state studiate diverse geometrie dei dissipatori ad attrito e dei relativi assieme trave-colonna. Le analisi ad elementi finiti hanno confermato l'efficacia delle ipotesi progettuali, nonché le prestazioni soddisfacenti dei nodi investigati.*

KEYWORDS: *nodi di acciaio, collegamenti trave-colonna, risposta sismica, dissipatore ad attrito, analisi agli elementi finiti*